

Isomerism in heterometallic trinuclear complexes with salen type Schiff base ligands[†]

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The use of neutral Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes of salen type Schiff bases as metalloligand in the synthesis of heterometallic polynuclear complexes are known since long but the potential of isomerization phenomenon in the resulted complexes has not been realized. A systematic study in the authors' laboratory for the last ten years revealed that the trinuclear heterometallic complexes can exist in different isomeric forms e.g. linear-bent isomers, linkage isomers, coordination position isomers, supramolecular isomers, polymorphs, etc. The focus of the present review is mainly on the syntheses, structural characterization and magnetic properties of these isomeric products.

Keywords: Isomerism, salen type Schiff base, metalloligand, heterometallic, crystal structures.

Introduction

Isomers are substances that have the same number and kinds of atoms with different arrangements. Isomerism is an important aspect of coordination complexes not only because it helped Alfred Werner to establish his coordination theory but it is also invaluable for the understanding of the existence of different structural varieties of a molecule and the subtle difference in the structure-reactivity or structure-property relationship of the molecules¹. Various types of isomerism, e.g. ionization, hydrate, linkage, polymerization, geometric (*cis-trans*, *fac-mer*), optical etc. are well documented since the time of Werner². Formation of different isomers in solid state depends upon various factors e.g. coordinative flexibility and lability of the metal ions, the versatility of coordination modes of the ligands, solubility of the different species formed in the solutions etc.³⁻⁵.

Since the work of Hugo Schiff (1864), a variety of Schiff bases have been synthesized and used as ligands for the formation of coordination complexes with different metal ions⁶. Among them, arguably the most popular class of ligands is

the [2+1] condensation products of salicylaldehyde or its derivatives and ethylenediamine or its homologues, which are termed as salen type (salen = 'sal' for salicylaldehyde + 'en' for ethylenediamine) Schiff base ligand⁷. The Schiff bases are known to react readily with transition metal ions to form coordination complexes since long⁸. Till 1960s, the complexes of such ligands had been characterized mostly by different spectroscopic techniques such as NMR, EPR, IR, UV-Vis-NIR and PMR along with elemental analyses and TGA. In 1960, structure of a Schiff base bound metal complex (*N,N'*-salicylidene-ethylenediamine-copper(II)) was first determined by single crystal X-ray crystallography⁹. It is now well known that these salen type di-negative Schiff bases act as chelating tetradentate N₂O₂ donor ligands and with divalent metal ions (e.g. Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} etc.) form neutral mononuclear complexes¹⁰. However, the oxygen atoms of the coordinated Schiff base, which are at close vicinity in the complex (*cis*-oriented in square planar or octahedral geometry), still contain free lone pairs of electrons which can be donated to another metal ion i.e. the complex itself can act as a chelating ligand to form polynuclear complexes. This "com-

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plex as a ligand" or "metalloligand" synthetic approach was proposed and applied successfully first by Ekk Sinn *et al.* in 1968 to synthesize several hetero-metallic complexes¹¹. He pointed out that the nuclearity of the resulting complexes could be di-, tri- or tetranuclear depending upon the numbers of metalloligands that coordinate to the second metal ion. The first X-ray crystallographic evidences for hetero-metallic trinuclear, [(CuL)₂Na(ClO₄)] and dinuclear [(CuL)Co(hfa)₂] complexes (hfa = hexafluoroacetylacetonate) were provided by Truter *et al.* (1968)¹² and Drago *et al.* (1973)¹³, respectively and that for homo-metallic dinuclear complex [(CuL)CuCl₂] by Sinn *et al.* (1972)¹⁴ and trinuclear complexes [(CuL)₂Cu(H₂O)₂](ClO₄)₂ by Willis *et al.* (1974)¹⁵. In the year 1985, Gatteschi *et al.* used this approach to synthesize two trinuclear 3d-4f complexes, [(CuL)₂Gd(H₂O)₃](ClO₄)₃ (L = two different types of salen type di-Schiff base ligands) and determined their structures by X-ray crystallography¹⁶. After that, some more dinuclear and trinuclear complexes were synthesized using this metalloligand approach by various groups¹⁷. Recently, we extensively developed this approach to obtain a rich variety of homo- and heteronuclear complexes, ranging from discrete di-, tri- and tetranuclear species to coordination polymers¹⁸. On the course of our investigations, we succeeded in isolating the trinuclear species in various isomeric forms such as linear-bent isomers, linkage isomers, coordination position isomers, supramolecular isomers, polymorphs, etc.¹⁹⁻²⁷.

In this review, we summarize these isomeric phenomena with examples. Till date, as we did not find any report on such isomerism in this type of heterometallic trinuclear complexes of salen type Schiff bases by any other group, the examples are given only from the published papers of our group¹⁹⁻²⁷.

Linear-bent (*transoid-cisoid*) isomerism

Reaction of metalloligand, [CuL^I] (where H₂L^I = *N,N'*-bis(salicylidene)-1,3-propanediamine) with Zn²⁺ in presence of azide ion resulted in two isomeric, trinuclear copper(II)-zinc(II) complexes, [(CuL^I)₂Zn(N₃)₂] (**1A** and **1B**) under different reaction conditions (Scheme 1)¹⁹.

Complex **1A** separated as a brown solid when the solution was stirred after mixing the components at room tem-

perature. The diffraction quality rhombic shaped reddish-brown single crystals of **1A** were obtained on keeping the filtrate overnight at open atmosphere. However, when the same reaction mixture was warmed in a water bath, then green crystalline compound along with X-ray quality single crystals were separated out from the hot solution. The green product was pure **1B** as was evident from its powder XRD pattern. When this green compound (**1B**) was dissolved in methanol and the solution was kept at room temperature for slow evaporation of solvent, the brown crystals of **1A** separated out. Similarly, a methanol solution of **1A** yielded the green crystalline compound of **1B** on keeping it on a water bath. However, isomers **1A** and **1B** showed hardly any change in their respective powder XRD patterns or colour on heating the solid compounds up to 200°C, after which they started to decompose. Therefore, it has been concluded that isomers **1A** and **1B** are interconvertible in solutions but not in the solid state.

Scheme 1. Formation of complexes **1A** and **1B**.

Complexes, **1A** and **1B** have the same molecular formula but crystallize in different crystal systems (triclinic for **1A** and monoclinic for **1B**) with space group $P\bar{1}$ for **1A** and $P2_1/c$ for **1B**. **1A** is an angular trinuclear species, in which two terminal four-coordinate square planar "metalloligand" [CuL^I] are coordinated to a central Zn^{II} through double phenoxido bridges. The Zn^{II} is in a six-coordinate distorted octahedral environment being bonded additionally to two mutually *cis* nitrogen atoms of terminal azide ions. In complex **1B**, in addition to the double phenoxido bridge, the two

terminal Cu^{II} ions are linked to the central Zn^{II} via a $\mu_{1,1}$ -azido bridge giving rise to a square pyramidal environment around the Cu^{II} ions and consequently the structure becomes linear. Therefore, these two isomeric species are termed as "linear" and "bent" isomers. EPR spectra and ESI mass spectra showed that the two isomers were identical in solution. The DFT calculation revealed that the energy of **1A** was 7.06 kcal/mol higher than that of **1B**. The existence of both isomers in the solid state suggested that crystal packing interactions in **1A** were more efficient and probably compensated the difference in energies between the discrete trinuclear forms.

Another pair of *transoid-cisoid* structures $[\{(\text{CuL}^1)(\text{Me}(\text{CO})\text{Me})\}_2\text{Dy}(\text{NO}_3)_3]$ (**2A**) and $[(\text{CuL}^1)_2\text{Dy}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{NO}_3)_3] \cdot \text{MeOH}$ (**2B**) have been synthesized by reacting the metalloligand, $[\text{CuL}^1]$ with $\text{Dy}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ (2:1) in acetone and methanol solvents, respectively²⁰. A relatively nonpolar aprotic solvent like acetone helped to assemble *transoid* structure **2A**, whereas polar protic methanol assisted the formation of *cisoid* structure **2B** as shown in Scheme 2. Other solvents, for example, ethanol and acetonitrile, also favored the formation of the *cisoid* complex, **2B**. The phase purity of both **2A** and **2B** has been confirmed from identity of the powder X-ray diffraction patterns, indicating each isomeric structure was formed exclusively.

Scheme 2. Formation of complexes **2A** and **2B**.

The structures of complexes, **2A** and **2B** were characterized by single crystal X-ray crystallography. The space group

of the crystal **2A** is tetragonal $I4_1/a$ with $Z = 8$. In **2A**, two metalloligand units $[\text{CuL}^1]$ serve as a chelating ligand to the central Dy^{3+} ion via bidentate μ_2 -phenoxido oxygen atoms in approximately coplanar orientation, making the $[\text{CuL}^1]_2\text{Dy}$ cluster as a *transoid* coordination. In addition, three chelating nitrate coligands [two are bridging μ_3 -nitrito-O and remaining one is terminally coordinated via O-atom] are bonded to the Dy center, building up deca-coordination with distorted tetradecahedron geometry. In contrast, for complex **2B**, the two metalloligands coordinated to the Dy^{3+} ions in an asymmetric angular orientation, making the coordination geometry of the trinuclear core *cisoid*. The space group of **2B** is $P\bar{1}$ with $Z = 2$. Two chelating nitrate and one coordinated water molecule build up the nona-coordination of Dy center, forming approximately a tricapped trigonal prism. The third nitrate ligand is axially coordinated to the terminal Cu atom of one of the coordinated metalloligands.

Both the compounds showed slow relaxation of magnetization but the effective energy barriers, U_{eff} of the magnetization reversal were found to be significant for the two isomers. The exchange coupling parameters $J_{\text{Dy-Cu}}$ of **2A** and **2B** were determined by recording HF-EPR spectra of a powder specimen and the values were found to be 2.25 ± 0.05 and 1.82 ± 0.04 , respectively. Thus, these two compounds provided insight into the dependence of magnetic coupling and single molecule magnet characteristics on the slight differences in the geometry around Ln ion, and their bond distances and angles.

Linkage isomerism

The reaction of metalloligand $[\text{CuL}^2]$ (where $\text{H}_2\text{L}^2 = N,N'$ -bis(salicylidene)-1,4-butanediamine) with $\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ in presence of NH_4SCN in methanol solution yielded a trinuclear hetero-metallic copper(II)-cadmium(II) complex, $[(\text{CuL}^2)_2\text{Cd}(\text{NCS})_2]$ (**3A**) (Scheme 3)²¹. Structural characterization of the complex revealed that complex **3A** is an angular trinuclear species, in which two terminal four-coordinate square planar "metalloligands" $[\text{CuL}^2]$ are coordinated to a central Cd^{II} through double phenoxido bridges along with two mutually *cis* nitrogen atoms of terminal thiocyanate ions. However, when the Schiff base was reduced ($\text{H}_2\text{L}^{2\text{R}}$, N,N' -bis(2-hydroxybenzyl)-1,4-butanediamine) and its Cu^{II} com-

plex, $[\text{CuL}^{2\text{R}}]$ was allowed to react with $\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ in presence of NH_4SCN under the same reaction conditions, complex $[(\text{CuL}^{2\text{R}})_2\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2]$ (**3B**) was produced. **3B** is also a trinuclear complex but it is linear in which in addition to the double phenoxido bridge, two SCN^- coordinate to the *trans* positions of the central octahedral Cd^{II} via S atoms. Thus, the coordination mode of thiocyanate is N-bonded in **3A** but S-bonded in **3B**. Theoretical calculations on the energetic difference between the two possible terminal coordination modes of the thiocyanate anion (monodentate, not bridging ligand) to the Cd atom reveal that N-coordination is more stable than S-coordination in agreement with the much greater abundance of the reported N-bonded structures of Cd^{II} in the literature. To provide an explanation for the change of coordination mode of the thiocyanate from usual N-coordination to rather unusual S-coordination on the reduction of C=N groups, the geometric and energetic features of the structures were analysed theoretically. It has been found that the reduction of imine to amine provides two H-bond donors which form strong H-bond with the N-atoms of the S-coordinated thiocyanate in **3B**. The binding energy of these hydrogen bonds was computed and the value was found to be more than the energy required to compensate the formation of less favoured Cd-SCN coordination. The experimental observations and theoretical calculations on these structures clearly show that only the electronic and steric effects may not explain the 'ambidentate' coordination behaviour of thiocyanate to Cd^{II} exclusively; in some cases, the weak inter-

actions such as H-bonding can also be crucial for the observed coordination mode.

Coordination position isomerism

The reaction of "metalloligand" $[\text{NiL}^1]$ with zinc perchlorate and ammonium thiocyanate, at room temperature, resulted in three different heterometallic complexes: $[(\text{NiL}^1)_2\text{Zn}(\text{NCS})_2]$ (**4**), $[(\text{NiL}^1)_2\text{Zn}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})_2] \cdot 2\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ (**5A**) and $\{[(\text{NiL}^1)_2\text{Zn}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})_2]\} \{[(\text{NiL}^1)_2\text{Zn}(\text{NCS})_2]\}$ (**5**), depending on the molar ratios of the reactants (Scheme 4)²². When $[\text{NiL}^1]$, Zn^{II} and SCN^- were mixed in 2:1:2 molar ratio, then a brown microcrystalline product of complex **4** was obtained. It crystallizes as brown rhombic-shaped single crystals. Complex **5A** was synthesized by using the same components but with an increase in the proportion of "metalloligand" $[\text{NiL}^1]$ i.e. mixing $[\text{NiL}^1]$, Zn^{II} and SCN^- in a 4:1:2 molar ratios. It crystallizes as blue rhombic-shaped single crystals. Finally, when $[\text{NiL}^1]$, Zn^{II} and SCN^- were mixed in a 1:1:2 molar ratio at room temperature, i.e. decreasing the proportion of "metalloligand" $[\text{NiL}^1]$, a red solid was isolated from the reaction mixture. The isolated red product is pure **5**. Red needle shaped X-ray quality single crystals of **5** were obtained by the slow evaporation of the filtrate in open atmosphere. It should be noted that both complexes **5A** and **5** were transformed to **4** when these were dissolved in methanol separately and the solutions were kept at room temperature for slow evaporation. On the other hand, complex **4** did not change to any other form upon recrystallization.

Scheme 3. The synthesis of **3A** and **3B**.

In **4**, the two terminal square planar Ni atoms and the central octahedral zinc atom are arranged in a bent structure where two *cis* N-bonded thiocyanate ions are coordinated to the central atom. The chemical composition of **5A** is very similar to that of **4**, but in **5A**, the central Zn atom is tetrahedral and the two N-bonded thiocyanate ions occupy axial position of each terminal Ni atom. Complex **5** consists of two closely related trinuclear units **5A** and **5B**. Complex **5B** is a "coordination position isomer" of complex **4** with the central square pyramidal Zn and one of the terminal square pyramidal Ni atoms coordinated by two N-bonded thiocyanate ions. Complex **5** is a unique example of a cocrystal formed by two similar trinuclear units (**5A** and **5B**).

Scheme 4. Synthesis of complexes **4**, **5A** and **5** (**5A** and **5B**).

Supramolecular isomerism

“Supramolecular isomerism” in coordination polymers is defined as the existence of more than one type of network superstructure or different architectures for the same molecular building blocks that have identical chemical compositions. Using the flexible trinuclear heterometallic complex $[(CuL^1)_2Cd]^{2+}$ as node and dicyanamide ion as spacers, three supramolecular isomers $\{[(CuL^1)_2Cd]_2(\mu_{1,5}\text{-}N(CN)_2)_2\}(ClO_4)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ (**6**), $\{[(CuL^1)_2Cd]_2(\mu_{1,3,5}\text{-}N(CN)_2)_2\}(ClO_4)_2\}_n$ (**7**), and $\{[(CuL^1)_2Cd(\mu_{1,5}\text{-}N(CN)_2)](ClO_4)\}_n$ (**8**) have been synthesized (where $H_2L^1 = N,N'$ -bis(salicylidene)-1,3-propanediamine) (Scheme 5)²³. Complex **6** separated as a brown solid when $[CuL^1]$, cadmium perchlorate and sodium dicyanamide were mixed in a 2:1:1 molar ratio in methanol at room temperature. The rectangular shaped brown single crystals of **6** were obtained on keeping the filtrate overnight at open atmosphere. The product remained the same if the reaction was carried out at a lower temperature. Interestingly, when the same reaction mixture was refluxed for about 10 h, a green compound was separated and the filtrate on slow evaporation at room temperature yielded the rectangu-

lar shaped green single crystals of **7**. However, when the same components were mixed in 2:3:1 molar ratio at room temperature, compound **8** was separated as a greenish brown crystalline solid. These compounds are interconvertible in solution. For example, when the brown compound **6** was dissolved in methanol and the solution was refluxed for 10 h, then the green crystals of **7** separated out. Compound **8** could also be converted to **7** in a similar way. However, compound **7** did not transform into **6** or **8**, indicating that it is the thermodynamically stable isomer. The simultaneous TG-DTA analyses and powder XRD patterns of the heated samples of compounds **6-8** indicated that there was no solid state transformation between these isomers on heating up to 150°C.

Scheme 5. Formation of complexes **6-8**.

Structural analyses show that complex **6** is a discrete hexanuclear cluster where two trinuclear nodes are connected through the Cd centres by convergent double $\mu_{1,5}$ -dicyanamido spacers. Complex **7** is a 1D stair coordination polymer, in which the hexanuclear units are joined by the coordination of the central nitrogen atom of a $\mu_{1,3,5}$ -dicyanamido ligand to the Cu atom of another unit. In contrast, complex **8** is a 1D zigzag chain, formed by connecting the Cd centre of trinuclear nodes via divergent $\mu_{1,5}$ -dicyanamido spacers. These three complexes contain a common $[(CuL^1)_2Cd(N(CN)_2)]ClO_4$ trinuclear unit as the molecu-

lar building block and represent "supramolecular isomerism" of 0D/1D coordination polymers.

In another study, two new hetero-metallic Cu^{II}-Zn^{II} isomeric compounds, [(CuL¹)₂Zn(μ_{1,5}-N(CN)₂)₂]_n (**9A**) and [(CuL¹)₂Zn(μ_{1,5}-N(CN)₂)₂]_n (**9B**) have been synthesized (Scheme 6) by reacting [CuL¹] with zinc perchlorate hexahydrate and sodium dicyanamide²⁴. Isomer **9A** was separated as yellowish green rhombic shaped crystals when "metalloligand" [CuL¹] (where H₂L¹ = *N,N'*-bis(salicylidene)-1,3-propanediamine), zinc perchlorate hexahydrate and sodium dicyanamide were reacted in 1:2:4 molar ratios in methanol-water mixture. On the other hand, when the same components as for **9A** were mixed in 2:1:2 molar ratios, a deep green hexagonal shaped crystalline product of isomer **9B** was obtained. The purity of **9A** and **9B** were checked by powder XRD patterns. In the formation of isomers **9A** and **9B**, the molar ratio of [CuL¹] and zinc(II) salt was crucial: when the ratio was 1:2 the product is **9A** but with a higher proportion of [CuL¹] the isomer **9B** started to appear and at their molar ratios of 2:1 or higher, **9B** became the sole product.

Other external factors such as temperature or concentration were found to have no effect on their formation. Isomer **9A** was transformed into **9B** by recrystallization from methanol at room temperature whereas **9B** was converted to **9A** by the addition of an excess of Zn^{II} salt (**9B**:Zn(ClO₄)₂ = 1:3) in a methanol solution. The TGA/DSC studies of isomers **9A** and **9B** indicated no solid state transformation between these isomers on heating.

Isomers **9A** and **9B** are constructed by the same trinuclear nodes [(CuL¹)₂Zn]²⁺ and dicyanamide spacers. In both of them, the trinuclear node are angular with similar conformation, the dicyanamido spacers are V-shaped and mutually *cis* coordinated to the central zinc atom, other end of which coordinate to the axial positions of the copper atoms of two different trinuclear units. As a result, every trinuclear unit is connected to four adjacent units through a single μ_{1,5}-dicyanamido bridge between copper and zinc atoms. However, the difference in structure arises from different spatial orientation of the dicyanamido linkers; the five trinuclear units in **9A** lie almost in the same plane, whereas in **9B** there are

only three units in the same plane. This kind of identical connectivity but different spatial orientation of the spacer results in supramolecular isomerism in the form of 2D (**9A**) and 3D (**9B**) coordination networks.

Two other very similar 2D/3D supramolecular isomers have been prepared by joining "metalloligand" [CuL¹] to Co^{II} with the help of dicyanamide spacers. Here the isomers were produced as a mixture when the [CuL¹] was reacted with cobalt(II) perchlorate and sodium dicyanamide in methanol-water medium²⁵. The colour of isomer **10A** is greenish-brown, whereas complex **10B** is green and this difference allowed them to separate in pure form easily by naked eye detection. The purity of the complexes has been confirmed by powder X-ray diffraction. The structures of **10A** and **10B** are very similar to those of **9A** and **9B**, respectively. Variable-temperature magnetic susceptibility measurements showed the presence of moderate antiferromagnetic exchange interactions (ferrimagnetic) in both the cases mediated through the double phenoxido bridges that have been fitted with an anisotropic model including spin-orbit coupling in the central Co^{II} ion.

Scheme 6. Formation of complexes **9A** and **9B**.

A case of solvent templated supramolecular isomerism was observed when the metalloligand [NiL¹] was reacted with Co(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O in presence of sodium dicyanamide in different solvents. From methanol solution, a two-dimensional (4,4) connected rhombic grid network of [(NiL¹)₂Co(NCNCN)₂]

(**11A**) was isolated whereas in acetonitrile solvent, a different species $\{[(\text{NiL}^1)_2\text{Co}(\text{NCNCN})_2] \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{CN}\}$ (**11B**) with a two-dimensional (4,4) connected square grid network was formed (Scheme 7)²⁶. The presence of acetonitrile molecules in the structure of **11B** seems to change the spatial orientation of the terminal metalloligands $[\text{NiL}^1]$ from pseudo-eclipsed in **11A** to staggered-like in **11B** around the central Co^{II} . These structural changes in the nodes together with the difference in the conformation of the dicyanamido spacers, which are *cis* coordinated to the Co^{II} in both trinuclear units, led to the formation of two different 2D networks. Variable-temperature magnetic susceptibility measurements revealed a drastic difference in magnetic properties: **11A** is an antiferromagnetically coupled spin-frustrated species while **11B** showed a dominant ferromagnetic coupling. The changes of the magnetic properties were explained by considering the geometrical differences in the phenoxido bridged Ni_2Co units which

are scalene triangular in **11A** but nearly linear in **11B**. The DFT calculations of exchange interactions between metal centres provided a clear evidence of the role played by the fundamental geometrical factors on the nature and magnitude of the magnetic coupling in these two isomeric structures.

Polymorphism

Polymorphs are the species with identical chemical composition and the same molecular connectivity, but exist in the solid state at least in two different arrangements of the molecules. During the course of our work with the synthesis of trinuclear heterometallic complexes, we isolated two pairs of polymorphs. The metalloligand, $[\text{NiL}^1]$ on reaction with cadmium perchlorate and sodium thiocyanate in $\text{MeOH-H}_2\text{O}$ medium (20:1, v/v) resulted in a pair of polymorphs $[(\text{NiL}^1)_2\text{Cd}(\text{NCS})_2]$ (**12A**) and $[(\text{NiL}^1)_2\text{Cd}(\text{NCS})_2]$ (**12B**) de-

Scheme 7. Upper panel: Formation of the structures of **11A** and **11B**. Lower panel: 2D extended coordination network along the crystallographic *ab* plane for **11A** (left side) and 2D extended coordination network along the crystallographic *ab* plane for **11B** (right side).

pending upon the reaction conditions (Scheme 8)^{27a}. Polymorph **12A** separated as a reddish yellow solid when the solution was refluxed for about 10 h after mixing the components. The diffraction quality rhombic shaped yellow single crystals of **12A** were obtained on keeping the filtrate overnight at open atmosphere. On the other hand, complex **12B** separated as an orange solid when the solution was stirred at room temperature.

The diffraction quality rectangular shaped orange single crystals of **12B** were obtained on keeping the filtrate overnight at open atmosphere. Doing the experiments at different temperatures, it was concluded that **12B** is formed when the constituents are mixed at room temperature or at low temperature but at higher temperature (when the mixture is put under reflux) **12B** transforms to **12A**.

When a similar experiment was performed with metalloligand $[\text{CuL}^1]$, again two polymorphs, $[(\text{CuL}^1)_2\text{Cd}(\text{NCS})_2]$ (**13A** and **13B**)^{27b} were produced under the similar conditions (Scheme 8). Crystals of **13A** were rhombic shaped and deep brown whereas those of **13B** were rectangular shaped and light brown. Here also higher temperature (under reflux) favoured the formation of **13A** whereas at lower temperature **13B** was the major product.

Besides the difference in colour and shape, the IR spectra of the polymorphs showed characteristic differences. For **12A**, a strong and broad peak at 2068 cm^{-1} (2068 cm^{-1} for **13A**) along with a shoulder at 2033 cm^{-1} (2030 cm^{-1} for **13A**) appeared, while for **12B** there was only a single strong and sharp peak at 2050 cm^{-1} (2055 cm^{-1} for **13B**). The splitting of the stretching vibration of thiocyanate in spectra of **12A** (or **13A**) was attributed to the presence of two different types of SCN^- groups in these two species as was confirmed by their crystal structures.

Structural analyses reveal that all these complexes are discrete trinuclear entities in which two square planar $[\text{NiL}^1]$ (or $[\text{CuL}^1]$) units are bonded to a cadmium ion through double phenoxido bridges. The Cd^{II} is in a six-coordinate distorted octahedral environment being bonded additionally to two mutually *cis* nitrogen atoms of terminal thiocyanate. Complex **12A** (or **13A**) crystallized in space group $P2_1/c$ whereas **12B** (or **13B**) in $P2_1/n$. The difference in the molecular

structures in the two sets of polymorphs seemed to originate from the different degree of distortion particularly in the bond angles around the cadmium atom. The two *cis* angles around the cadmium atom, which are originated from the O atoms of two different "metalloligands" are considerably different in the polymorphs. In the case of 'A' set both these *cis* angles are significantly greater than 90° whereas the *trans* angle is less than 180° by 18.5° and 16.6° for **12A** and **13A**, respectively. On the other hand, in the 'B' set, one *cis* angle is less while the other one is greater than 90° . The corresponding *trans* angle is smaller by 36.4° and 35.9° for **12B** and **13B**, respectively from the ideal value of 180° . The relative disposition of the two "metalloligands" around the Cd atom is thus different: they slide away from each other more in the 'A' set than in the 'B' set resulting a greater Ni---Ni (or Cu---Cu) separation in the 'A' set.

Scheme 8. Formation of complexes of **12A** or **13A** and **12B** or **13B**.

A theoretical investigation shows that **12A** is slightly more (2.25 kcal/mol) stable than **12B**. However, in the crystal lattice, **12A** establishes a C-H/ π interaction while **12B** interacts through a C-H--S hydrogen bond to form dimer and the more favorable dimerization energy in the later (*ca.* 3 kcal/mol) compensates the difference in the relative energy of the polymorphs.

Conclusions

In the present review, emphasis is given mostly on the

synthetic and structural parts of various isomers which were isolated and characterized recently in our laboratory. It has been observed that almost in all cases the change in reaction conditions e.g. solvent, stoichiometric ratios of the reactants, temperature etc. played very important roles in the isolation of different isomers. The initial distinction between the isomers can be made by careful inspection of the colour and shape of the crystals and IR spectra which usually show some differences. Of course, single crystal X-ray analysis is essential to establish the structures of the isomers. In fact, during the course our work, growing single crystals of these compounds, especially in different isomeric forms was the most challenging. As we succeeded to overcome this challenge, we could develop the field of hetero-metallic complexes of salen-type Schiff base ligands by isolating complexes of different nuclearities and isomeric forms and rationalizing their formation by theoretical calculations. The isolation of different isomers provides an opportunity to scrutinize the subtle structural variations that influences the magnetic coupling and SMM properties of these polynuclear complexes.

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